

Transcript: "Methods of analysis of selected instrumental music pieces of the Sonnleithner Collection of Tyrol"

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If one tries to get hold of sheet music of various musical compositions – no matter which genre – nowadays, it is probably easier than it was 200 years ago. While today, thanks to the Internet, one can access various databases of sheet music, with libraries that are provided online, the question arises as to how 200 years ago sheet music was collected, how the collected material was processed and stored, and who was responsible for it. This also raises the question of how the collected pieces are analyzed. I would like to get to the bottom of this question in my talk, using Joseph Sonnleithner's folk song collection undertaking, which was initiated in 1819, as an example. On the basis of this collection, selected pieces of instrumental music will be analyzed in more detail.

Now briefly to the structure of my talk. First of all, I will deal with the Sonnleithner Collection of the Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde itself. In doing so, I will briefly discuss the following aspects: Who was Joseph Sonnleithner, how did he proceed with his undertaking, which geographical areas were included and were there already other comparable endeavors before the Sonnleithner Collection? Likewise, the question of the rediscovery of the Sonnleithner Collection will also be discussed in this context. In the case of the selected instrumental music pieces, I will show you some peculiarities and point out some methods of analysis.

In 1819, the first semi-official folk music collection, the so-called "Sonnleithner Collection", was initiated in the Austrian Crown Lands of the Habsburg Monarchy by the secretary of the Society of Friends of Music in Vienna, Joseph von Sonnleithner.

Slide

Briefly to his person, he was born on March 3rd, 1766 in Vienna and died on December 26th, 1835 also in Vienna. He was, among other things, a court official, theater secretary and librettist. For his collection enterprise, Sonnleithner made use of official channels in order to more easily achieve the desired results. To do this, he first needed the signature of the land marshal of Lower Austria and "president" of the Society of Friends of Music, Landgrave Joachim Egon von Fürstenberg (1749-1828). This was initially sufficient to give the project an "official character". The decisive permission to carry out the project, however, came from the then "Supreme Chancellor and Minister of the Interior," Franz Joseph Graf von Saurau (1760-1832). Saurau held several offices and was willing to have the project carried out for cultural-political reasons. The guidelines drawn up by Joseph

Sonnleithner were forwarded by Landgrave Fürstenberg to the Ministry of the Interior. The following materials were sought:

Slide

1. profane folk songs, arranged only for the singing voice.
2. the corresponding texts, as complete as possible, especially the older ones, with notes regarding the region in which are mostly sung.
3. melodies of the national dances, especially those that are performed at special festivities, weddings, or funeral ceremonies.
4. church songs that have been preserved for many years.
5. knowledge of the names of the promoters of music, in order to be able to enter into direct correspondence with them.

The call and the guidelines for collecting were sent to the district offices of the provinces of Tyrol, Illyria, Dalmatia, Styria, Upper Austria, Lower Austria, Bohemia, Moravia and Silesia. Within the scope of this talk, we will focus exclusively on submissions from the Tyrol. In general, it must be said that Sonnleithner's interest in musical folklife at the beginning of the 19th century was not unique. The collecting activities were in the spirit of contemporary Europe and were not limited to the Alpine region. At the beginning of the 19th century Achim von Arnim and Clemens Brentano published their song collection "Des Knaben Wunderhorn" (1805-1808) in three volumes and in 1807 the song collection "Stimmen der Völker in Liedern" by Johann Gottfried Herder was published posthumously. Also to be mentioned in this context are the folk song collectors Franz Tschischka and Julius Maximilian Schottky. Both went on a research trip to southern Lower Austria in 1817/18 to collect Austrian folk songs and fairy tales. In 1819 they published their book "Oesterreichische Volkslieder mit ihren Singeweisen".

Slide

Tyrol has also been inspired by "song collecting" for a long time. Thus, already at the beginning of the 19th century, the country judge Johann Strolz (1780-1835), born in Strass, collected some folk songs, which he published in 1807. After Sonnleithner's endeavor, the submissions were merely given archive numbers, but the members of the Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde did not comment on the contents of the collection or publish any of the musical material. It was not until 1913 (almost 100

years later) that the then archivist of the Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde Eusebius Mandyczewski (1857-1929) drew Raimund Zoder's (1882-1963) attention to the archive and thus the Sonnleithner Collection was rediscovered. Zoder strove to make parts of the material known and published some dances and songs from it. He was himself a teacher and elementary school director in Vienna from 1901-1931. However, he retired early in order to be able to devote himself entirely to folk music research.

Slide

It was not until the anniversary year 1969 (one hundred and fifty years of folk song research in Austria) that Leopold Schmidt (1912-1981), who was a folklorist at the Academy of Music and Performing Arts in Vienna, suggested that a catalog of the Sonnleithner Collection be compiled.

Walter Deutsch and Gerlinde Hofer followed Schmidt's initiative and published the first systematic arrangement of the collection in the book "Die Volksmusiksammlung der Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde in Wien" in 1969. In October 2001, the catalog was revised by Friederike Jary-Janecka.

Slide

The Tyrolean and Vorarlberg submissions comprise a total of 276 musical recordings, of which 119 are songs and 157 are instrumental pieces. The holdings are indicated in the systematization of Deutsch/Hofer under this shelfmark. The entire holdings of the Sonnleithner Collection are now in the archives of the Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde in Vienna and can be viewed there.

The collection from Tyrol and Vorarlberg can be divided into a total of five geographical areas: Pustertal, Bozen, Trento, Imst and Bregenz.

Slide

The Sonnleithner Collection contains songs and instrumental pieces for a wide variety of occasions. There are, among others, Christmas songs, inn songs, wedding songs, school songs and songs for church celebrations. On various holidays and on occasions like Christmas, Easter or Whitsuntide songs were sung and played. Among the instrumental music pieces there are German dances, minuets, rindi, ländler, waltzes, marches and contre dances. Songs and pieces for guitar, organ, violin, bass, swell, clarinet and piano were sent to Vienna. The collection from Tyrol and Vorarlberg is thus characterized by a wide range of instruments.

In the following illustration, the places from which songs and pieces have been preserved are shown in green. The order is based on the listing in the catalog of Deutsch/Hofer from 1969. Songs and instrumental music pieces were sent in from the following places:

Bruneck, Dietenheim, Taufers, Mühlbach, Michaelsburg, Toblach, Niederndorf, Welsberg, Bozen, Ritten, Klausen, Castel Ruth, Meran, Partschins, Lienz, Aßling, Aineth, Imst, Ehrenberg, Nauders Trient, Bregenz, Lustenau und Montafon.

The communities highlighted in red on the map received reply letters but no songs or pieces. Schwaz was contacted by the archives of the Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde, but neither the Tyrolean provincial archives nor the archives of the Gesellschaft der Musikfreunde in Vienna contain a letter of reply or songs or pieces. Schwaz thus remains the only one of those circles marked in red without a letter of reply.

In the following, some instrumental submissions are listed and analyzed. In the instrumental submissions of the Sonnleithner Collection of Tyrol, 118 pieces have no instrumentation. The occasion of the performance as well as the instrumentation can be partially reconstructed by comparing other pieces from the Sonnleithner Collection. In the following section, some pieces from the collection are presented and their musical characteristics are shown.

Slide

A total of 17 German dances (T XVI) have been preserved from Kastelruth and Meran. Like the entries from Klausen (T XV), they are notated in unison. If one compares the handwriting, it can be assumed that the dances all originate from the same scribe. The title page of the submission only reads "dances", with no indication of instrumentation. It is interesting to note that each individual dance is different and distinguished by its own structure and musical line. A large part of the dances, namely no. 4-13 are in 3/4 time, while dances no. 14-17 are in 3/8 time, dances no. 2 and 3 are in "alla-breve" and dance no. 1 is notated in 2/4 time. If we look at the keys of the dances, we can see that dances No. 1, 3-6, 8, 11, 13, 17 are in G major, dances 2, 7, 10, 12 are in D major, and dances 14-16 are in C major.

The pieces mentioned were sent by the school teacher and organist Mathias Ploner (*13.04.1770 Ortisei/South Tyrol, † 27.4.1845 Bressanone).

Slide

As a further example for analysis, we now look to a completely different corner of Tyrol, namely to Niederndorf. From the community of Niederndorf, not only songs, but also instrumental submissions with a note of the name have been preserved. In the case of the submission of the "6 Ländler" (T XI /9) for violin ("Violino Primo"), there is a note on the title page that says "Compose Michael Kramer Organist zu Niderdorf in Pusterthal. 1819.". As can be seen from the estate of the church choir in Niederndorf, the organist Michael Kramer left varying notations on his compositions.

- „Abgeschrieben im Monath October 1840. Kramer“,
- „Michael Kramer [mit Jahreszahl]“,
- „Scriptum Kramer [mit Jahreszahl]“,
- „Composé par Monsieur Kramer Organista in Parochia Absam 1817.“
- „Ex rebus Kramer [mit Jahreszahl]“
- „Scriptum Kramer pro anis [mit Jahreszahl]“
- „Authore Kramer [mit Jahreszahl]“
- „Michaele Kramer Organist in Niederdorf [mit Jahreszahl]“

Kramer left a large collection of sheet music in the music archive in Niederdorf, in which he appears as a scribe as well as a copyist. His life can be traced through the name notes along with their dates. In 1817 Kramer was an organist in Absam. On the basis of the 6 Ländler (T XI /9) sent to Vienna, it can be traced that he later worked as an organist in Niederdorf around 1819. In Niederdorf, he composed mainly sacred works such as masses, offertories and litanies. On his copies and compositions he left, in addition to the title, extremely precise instrumentation information.

Slide

Now let's go into the details. All 6 Ländler are written in 3/4 time. The Ländler no. 1 and 2 are in the key of C major, no. 3 and no. 4 in G major and no. 5 and 6 in F major. The scribe's precise dynamic indications in the Ländler are striking: f.[orte] and p.[iano]. Formally, the pieces form two 8-bar periods with repetition. Another peculiarity of the Ländler No. 2, No. 3, No. 4 and No. 5 is that they end in two voices in the final sound. If we look at Ländler No. 1, the first 8-bar period is in the dynamic indication of f and the second 8-bar period is in p. Ländler No. 2 is characterized by numerous staccato indications and Ländler No. 3 by a chromatic motive. Ländler No. 4 and No. 6 each begin with a triplet upbeat. The special feature of Ländler No. 5 is a grace note in bar 4. Ländler No. 1 in C major consists of the triads of the I. degree (C major) and the V. degree (G major). Likewise, Ländler No. 2 in which, briefly, the IV. degree (F major, in bar 12) makes an appearance. In Ländler No. 3, the I. degree (G major) and the V. degree (D major) are found. Ländler No. 4 consists mainly of the degrees I. (G major), IV. (C major), and V. (D major), or with added seventh V⁷. In Ländler No. 5 and Ländler No. 6, the I. degree (F major) and the V. degree (C major) – partly also with a seventh chord (V⁷) – would suffice for a harmonic embellishment. The 6 Ländler (T XI /9) were written by Michael Kramer, an organist active in the Niederdorf parish.

Slide

Another example of instrumental music from the Sonnleithner Collection of Tyrol is the South Tyrolean district of Ritten. From the correspondence concerning the Sonnleithner Collection, it can be seen that among the music promoters of the district of Ritten, "Ein Kirchengzug nebst einem Tafelstück und 2 deutschen Tänzen" (A church procession along with a table piece and 2 German dances) were sent in by Franz Überbacher, the organist in Lengmoos (*13.11.1795 "Sarnthal", †5.02.1853 Lengmoos/Ritten): "The new organist at Lengmoos Uiberpacher shows himself deserving of promotion in music among the peasantry". These four instrumental music pieces (T XIII /1-4) are the pieces "No 1 Kirchengzug Marsch" (T XIII /1), "Tafelstückl" (T XIII /2), "Deutscher Tanz" (T XIII /3) and "Kehraus" (T XIII /4). All pieces are notated in score form. The entries T XIII /2-4 are in the instrumentation of two violins, bass and swell. The "Kirchengzug Marsch" (T XIII /1), is played with the same instruments, but without the swell (Schwegelpfeife).

Slide

The entries T XIII /1 and 2 are in the key of D major in alla-breve. The pieces are mostly notated in two voices at the end of a musical phrase. T XIII /1 is headed "Majestoso.". The first period counts eight measures, the second has only seven measures. The melodic line of the first and second violins runs in parallel thirds. In the second period, the first violin plays triplets in the melody (measures 10-13).

In the following audio sample, "Kirchengzug Marsch," the instrumentation has been rearranged for a wind ensemble.

Slide

On the basis of the examples presented, it becomes clear that instrumental compositions can be analyzed or musically described in several ways. First of all, one can easily determine the key and the time signature. In addition, it can also be determined whether the piece is written for one or several voices. The tempo and the instrumentation – if available – are also important. Another aspect that should always be taken into account are the musical figures that appear in the pieces of the Sonnleithner Collection of Tyrol. These can mostly be stated by degrees, mainly by an interaction of tonic (I. degree) and dominant (V. degree). In the triads there is often a seventh in the Vth degree. Furthermore, there are special features in the motives of the dances handed down in the Sonnleithner Collection. Here chromatic and triplet figures are to be mentioned. In the case of polyphonic pieces, as is the case with the church procession march from Ritten, the voice leading can also be analyzed. Here, a parallel voice leading between first and second violin is evident.